

The Alkylation of Acetoacetic Ester by Toluenesulphonic Esters.

BY C. NARAYANAN NAIR AND D. H. PEACOCK.

Lapworth and Ferns (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 273) prepared a number of toluenesulphonic esters and used them in the preparation of ethers and amines. It was later found that toluenesulphonic ester could be used in the alkylation of malonic ester (Peacock and Tha, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 131, 2303) and the process has been applied by Slotta and Franke (*Ber.*, 1930, 63, 682), Clemo and Tenniswood (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2550), and Tabern and Volwiler (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 56, 1139). For the purpose of another investigation a series of ketones of the type $RR'CH\cdot CO\cdot Me$ was required and in the present paper it is shown that toluenesulphonic esters may be employed in the alkylation of acetoacetic ester. The toluenesulphonic esters employed were all derived from alcohols of the type $R\cdot O\cdot C_2H_4OH$, where R was an aromatic radical. These alcohols, which have previously been described by Boyd and Marle (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 2128), were prepared by the general method used by Peacock and Tha (*loc. cit.*). A number of toluenesulphonic esters are described as well as an improved method of preparation.

It was found that the rate of reaction between the ester and the sodium derivative of acetoacetic ester was accelerated by the addition of potassium iodide to the mixture; the effect was probably due to the intermediate formation of the iodide (*cf.* Peacock and Menon, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2, 240). The toluenesulphonic ester of phenol and of β -naphthol did not react with sodioacetoacetic ester.

EXPERIMENTAL.

β -Phenoxyethyl-p-toluenesulphonate.—The method previously described by Peacock and Tha (*loc. cit.*) has been improved. *p*-Toluenesulphonyl chloride (100 g.) was dissolved in acetone (400 c.c.), cooled to 10° and stirred. β -Phenoxyethyl alcohol (70 g.) and caustic soda solution (20%, 100 c.c.) were added gradually during about 2 hours. The temperature of the mixture was then allowed to rise to 30° to complete the reaction and the contents of the flask poured into cold water; the crude ester (135 g., 93%) then solidified. It was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 80°.

The toluenesulphonic esters of phenol (Reverdin and Crepieux, *Ber.*, 1902, 35, 1439) and β -naphthol were similarly prepared.

γ-Phenoxybutyric acid.—Sodium (2.3 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (90 c.c.) and acetoacetic ester (13 g.) and *β*-phenoxyethyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate (29.2 g.) added. The reaction mixture was boiled under reflux for 24 hours. The sodium *p*-toluenesulphonate was then filtered off and the alcohol removed from the filtrate by distillation. The crude ester was then saponified by heating with alcoholic caustic potash (20 g. of caustic potash in 40 c.c. of aqueous alcohol) for 8 hours. Water was added and the alcohol removed by distillation. The residue was extracted with benzene to remove neutral products and then acidified. The semi-solid acid was extracted with benzene leaving a sparingly soluble residue (B) and the acid fractionally extracted from the benzene with sodium bicarbonate solution. The first extracts on acidification gave *γ*-phenoxybutyric acid, m. p. 63° from petrol (Bentley, Haworth and Perkin, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1896, 69, 169, give m.p. 64-65°). [Found: Equiv (by titration) 182, (by silver salt), 182.5. $C_{10}H_{12}O_3$ requires Equiv., 180].

The later sodium bicarbonate extracts gave on acidification a substance identical with (B) above, m.p. 156-57° with evolution of carbon dioxide. It gave no colour with ferric chloride, M.W. (Rast) 210.

In the following table is shown the effect of the addition of potassium iodide to the reaction mixture. At the end of the time specified, excess of standard hydrochloric acid was added and the unused acid determined by titration with standard sodium carbonate solution. The percentage of sodium derivative used up was calculated from these figures.

Time of heating	...	1/2 hr.	1 hr.	3 hrs.
% of reaction without KI	...	22.1	36	48.4
" " with KI	...	30.6	43.5	61.3

γ-Phenoxypropyl methyl ketone. (Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 42, 651).—Acetoacetic ester (55 g.) was condensed with *β*-phenoxyethyl-*p*-toluenesulphonate (98 g.) in the way already described; the acetoacetic ester was in 25% excess and the reaction mixture was heated for 30 hours. The crude ester (80 g.) was saponified by heating for 16 hours with a solution of caustic potash (30 g. in rectified spirit (550 c.c.)). Alcohol (200 c.c.) was then distilled off and the residue heated for a further 5 hours. The alcohol was then removed by distillation under reduced pressure using a fractionating column and the residue steam distilled. The ketone solidified (80 g., 17%). It was crystallised from petrol ether, m.p. 53-54°. [Found: C, 73.86;

H, 8.21; M.W. (in acetic acid), 165.5. $C_{11}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 74.1; H, 7.86%. M.W., 178]. The residual aqueous solution gave γ -phenoxybutyric acid (4 g.) and $\beta\beta$ -diphenoxyethylacetic acid (3 g.). The ketone gave *semicarbazone*, which crystallised from aqueous alcohol, m.p. 144°. (Found: N, 17.8. $C_{12}H_{17}O_2N_3$ requires N, 17.8 per cent). The *oxime* crystallised from petrol ether, m.p. 78°. (Found: N, 7.3. $C_{11}H_{15}O_2N$ requires N, 7.2 per cent).

γ -Phenoxy- α -benzylbutyric acid.— α -Aceto- γ -phenoxybutyrate was prepared as already described and converted without isolation to the sodium compound and condensed with benzyl chloride by further heating for 4 hours. The crude ester (68 g.) was saponified by heating for 20 hours with alcoholic caustic potash (4g. in 100 c.c. of aqueous alcohol). The crude acid obtained from the potassium salt was distilled (b.p. 250-280°/35mm., yield 17g., 32%) and solidified on keeping. It was crystallised from petrol, m.p. 77°. [Found: Equiv. (by titration), 269.1; C, 75.75; H, 7.0. $C_{17}H_{18}O_3$ requires Equiv., 270; C, 75.55; H, 6.66 per cent). The acid was converted by thionyl chloride into the acid chloride and thence to the *amide*, crystals from dilute alcohol, m.p. 125-26°. (Found: N, 5.35. $C_{17}H_{19}O_2N$ requires N, 5.2 per cent). Ketonic hydrolysis failed to give the required ketone.

β -p-Chlorophenoxyethyl-p-toluenesulphonate.— β -p-Chlorophenoxyethyl alcohol (Boyd and Marle, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 103, 2128) was prepared by heating p-chlorophenol (128.5 g.), caustic soda (40 g. in 800 c.c. of water) and ethylene chlorhydrin (60 g.) under reflux on a sand-bath for 2 hours. The product was washed with caustic soda to remove the excess of p-chlorophenol, dried and distilled at 178°/35mm., yield 106 g.. This was converted to the toluenesulphonic ester in a way similar to that described for phenoxyethyl alcohol; yield of crude ester, 92%. Crystallised from methylated spirit, m.p. 79°. (Found: C, 54.89; H, 4.56. $C_{15}H_{15}O_4ClS$ requires C, 55.1; H, 4.59 per cent).

γ -p-Chlophenoxybutyric acid.—The above ester (20.4 g.) was heated for 30 hours with an absolute alcoholic solution of the sodium derivative of ethyl acetoacetate (8.13 g.) The crude ester (26 g.) was saponified by boiling with alcoholic caustic potash (7 g. in 40 c.c. of ethyl alcohol) for 11 hours. The crude acid was purified by solution in sodium bicarbonate and reprecipitation (yield 2.6g., 20%). After crystallisation from petrol ether it melted at 120°. [Found: Equiv. (by titration), 215; Cl, 16.3. $C_{10}H_{11}O_3Cl$ requires Equiv., 214.5; Cl, 16.5 per cent).

γ-p-Chlorophenoxypropyl methyl ketone.—The crude ketone, b.p. 170-195° / 35 mm., was obtained from the portion insoluble in caustic potash in the above preparation. The *semicarbazone* crystallised from methylated spirit, m.p. 178°. (Found: N, 15·3. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2N_3Cl$ requires N, 15·5 per cent).

β-m-Chlorophenoxyethyl-p-toluenesulphonate was prepared in a way similar as the *p*-isomer, m.p. 57°. (Found: Cl, 10·66. $C_{15}H_{15}O_4ClS$ requires Cl, 10·68 per cent).

γ-m-Chlorophenoxybutyric acid.—The above ester (11 g.) was condensed with the sodium derivative of ethyl acetoacetate (5 g.) by boiling in absolute alcohol solution for 30 hours, yield of crude ester 9·2 g. This was saponified by heating with caustic potash (5 g. in 25 c.c. of aqueous alcohol) for 11 hours. The acid obtained (1·8 g.) was crystallised from petrol ether, m.p. 51-52°. [Found: Equiv. (by titration), 216; Cl, 16·23. $C_{10}H_{11}O_3Cl$ requires Equiv., 214·5; Cl, 16·57 per cent].

γ-m-Chlorophenoxypropyl methyl ketone.—The crude ketone from the above preparation weighed 3 g., b.p. 180-200° / 35 mm. The *semicarbazone* crystallised from methylated spirit, m.p. 146°. (Found: N, 15·7. $C_{12}H_{16}O_2N_3Cl$ requires N, 15·5 per cent).

β-β-Naphthoxyethyl-p-toluenesulphonate.—The required alcohol was prepared from ethylene chlorhydrin and *β*-naphthol (*cf.* Boyd and Marle, *loc. cit.*) It was converted to the sulphonate as already described, yield 82%. It crystallised from methylated spirit, m.p. 90°. (Found: S, 9·03. $C_{19}H_{18}O_4S$ requires S, 9·35 per cent).

γ-β-Naphthoxybutyric acid.—The above ester (14 g.) was boiled for 30 hours with an absolute alcoholic solution of the sodium derivative of ethyl acetoacetate (5 g.) The crude ester (15 g.) was boiled for 4 hours with a solution of caustic potash (6 g. in 30 c.c. of ethyl alcohol). The crude acid (3 g.) crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 122°. [Found: Equiv. (by titration), 231·6; C, 72·6; H, 6·10. $C_{14}H_{14}O_3$ requires Equiv., 230; C, 73·0; H, 6·00 per cent].

γ-β-Naphthoxypropyl methyl ketone.—The crude ketone from the above preparation weighed 3 g., b.p. 220-230° / 25 mm. The *semicarbazone* crystallised from methylated spirit, m.p. 174°. (Found: N, 14·8. $C_{16}H_{19}O_2N_3$ requires N, 14·6 per cent).

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